

EVALUATION OF THE TRANSVERSE PERMEABILITY OF ALIGNED FIBERS IN COMPOSITE PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

In composite processing with aligned fibers, transverse permeability is found to be very different from that in the longitudinal direction. When the fiber volume fraction is relatively high, which is the performance requirement for most structural composites, transverse permeability is greatly influenced by the fiber packing status. In this study a self-consistent model containing variables of the fiber packing status is proposed. The derived expression for the transverse permeability contains two variables, the averaged fiber volume fraction and the maximum packing efficiency, which adequately describe the status of a fiber bundle and can be measured experimentally.

INTRODUCTION

Aligned and continuous fibers are widely used in composite reinforcement. During the fabrication of reinforced composite structures, resin flow through the fiber network is a key parameter to the process design and control. The permeability behavior of aligned fiber bundles is highly anisotropic. Flow resistance in the transverse direction to the fiber bundle is much higher than that of parallel or longitudinal direction. In the longitudinal or parallel direction, the flow is more close to the channel flow. In the transverse direction, the main flow resistance comes from many gaps among fibers.

The most widely used theory in modeling the permeability of aligned fibers is the Kozeny-Carman equation, in which the fiber volume fraction V_f is chosen as the main parameter. Many studies show that within the fiber volume fraction range in the composite processing area, Kozeny-Carman equation is a good approximation [1-6]. When permeability in different directions is considered, one option is to use different values of Kozeny constant [3]. However, theoretically the permeable flow may be stopped in the transverse direction when the maximum packing efficiency is reached. Kozeny-Carman equation cannot predict this behavior of a fiber bundle. Modified forms of Kozeny-Carman equation has been proposed [2, 4].

When self-consistent method (SCM) is proposed to estimate the permeability of an aligned fiber bundle, a basic element of a heterogeneous medium is considered as being embedded in an equivalent homogeneous medium whose properties are unknown and to be determined. The consistent conditions are that the total amount of the flow and the dissipation energy remain the same with and without the insertion. Permeability can be derived as a function of the fiber volume fraction, but the stop-flow phenomenon cannot be predicted.

As an alternative of the self-consistent method, the improved self-consistent method (ISCM) is proposed. The introduction of an additional variable V_a , the ultimate fiber volume fraction, effectively captures the geometry characteristics of the flow resistance in the transverse direction. As a comparison we present here both methods. Comparison with available numerical and experimental data is also included. The illustration of both models is given in Fig. 1.

SELF-CONSISTENT MODEL

As shown in the figure, the insertion with radius b containing a fiber of radius a is placed into the homogeneous medium with the transverse permeability K_z . There exist three distinct regions, 1) $r \leq a$; 2) $a \leq r \leq b$; and 3) $r \geq b$. For region 2, the fluid flow can be described by the Stokes flow. For regions 3, Darcy's law can be applied. We assume that at infinity $V_y=0$ and $V_z=V_\infty$, where y axis lies at $\theta=0$ of the corresponding cylindrical system. The pressure gradient, which is the driving force for the fluid motion, is therefore only in the z direction (or $\theta=90^\circ$). Since the consistent conditions require that the flow in the outside field, or region 3, is not disturbed with the insertion, only fluid flow in region 2 is solved.

In the 2-D domain, the equation using the stream function ψ is

$$\nabla^4 \psi = 0 \quad (1)$$

The velocity components in the cylindrical coordinate system are defined as

$$V_r = -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \theta}$$

$$V_\theta = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} \quad (2)$$

The boundary conditions at the inner surface $r=a$ are

$$(V_r)_{r=a} = 0$$

$$(V_\theta)_{r=a} = 0 \quad (3)$$

At the interface $r=b$, the velocity component in the radial direction must be continuous. This gives

$$(V_r)_2 = (V_r)_3 \quad (4)$$

The shear stress at the inside region goes to zero. In the cylindrical coordinate system this becomes

$$(\sigma_{r\theta})_{r=b} = \mu \left[r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{V_\theta}{r} \right) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial V_r}{\partial \theta} \right]_{r=b} = 0 \quad (5)$$

This last condition of the shear stress is equivalent to the normal stress condition at the interface, $(\sigma_{rr})_2 = -p_3$.

The consistent condition of the dissipation energy states that the total dissipation energy with the porous medium and with the insertion must be the same. This can be written as

$$E = \frac{\mu}{K_z} \pi b^2 V_\infty^2 = \int_a^b \int_0^{2\pi} 2\mu \left[\left(\frac{\partial V_r}{\partial r} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial V_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{V_r}{r} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial V_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial V_\theta}{\partial r} - \frac{V_\theta}{r} \right)^2 \right] r \, d\theta \, dr \quad (6)$$

These equations complete the problem statements. With the consideration of the symmetric condition and the far-field velocity distribution, the solution of ψ is

$$\psi = \left[A_2 \frac{r}{b} + B_2 \left(\frac{r}{b} \right)^3 + C_2 \left(\frac{r}{b} \right)^{-1} + D_2 \left(\frac{r}{b} \right) \ln \left(\frac{r}{b} \right) \right] \cos \theta \quad (7)$$

where A_2 , B_2 , C_2 , and D_2 are constants to be determined using interface conditions. The final solution of the permeability by using the normalized form is

$$K_z^* = \frac{K_z}{r_f^2} = \frac{1}{8 V_f} \left(\ln \frac{1}{V_f} - \frac{1 - V_f^2}{1 + V_f^2} \right) \quad (8)$$

with $V_f = a^2/b^2$. Same result is also presented in [7] with a slightly different consideration. However, the other option for the interface condition at $r=b$ is

$$\begin{aligned} r=b: \quad (V_r)_2 &= (V_r)_3 \\ (V_\theta)_2 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

With this option, the corresponding normalized transverse permeability becomes

$$K_z^* = \frac{1 - V_f}{V_f} \frac{(1 - V_f) + \frac{1}{2}(1 + V_f) \ln V_f}{(1 + V_f^2) \ln V_f - (1 - V_f)(7 - V_f)} \quad (10)$$

Although the expressions are quite different, they show very similar trend as seen in Fig. 2. When compared with Kozeny-Carman equation backed by experimental results [3], the solution of the permeability with the stress condition is higher than the empirical formula predictions, while the solution with the velocity condition is lower. With only fiber volume fraction as the variable, none of these formulas can predict the stop-flow phenomenon at the maximum packing efficiency.

IMPROVED SELF-CONSISTENT MODEL

In this approach, the insertion of radius b consists of two parts, a circular section with radius a of fluid, and a ring section of a porous medium between a and b with the permeability of the hexagonal packing, K_{zh} . Therefore, there are still three distinct regions,

1) $r \leq a$; 2) $a \leq r \leq b$; and 3) $r \geq b$. For region 1, the fluid flow can be described by the Stokes flow. For regions 2 and 3, Darcy's law can be applied. The assumed far-field conditions are the imposed velocity distribution as stated before.

1) Region of $r \leq a$. By using the stream function ψ , we have the similar flow equation. The solution satisfying the velocity distributions is

$$\psi = \left[A_1 \frac{r}{a} + B_1 \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^3 + C_1 \left(\frac{r}{a} \right)^{-1} + D_1 \frac{r}{a} \ln \frac{r}{a} \right] \cos \theta \quad (11)$$

Because at the point $r=0$, V_r and V_θ are finite, $C_1=D_1=0$.

2) Region of $a \leq r \leq b$. The equation for the pressure is

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial \theta^2} = 0 \quad (12)$$

By using Darcy's law and taking into account the flow distribution, we have

$$(q_r)_2 = - \frac{K_{zh}}{\mu} \left(A_2 \sin \theta - \frac{A'_2}{r^2} \sin \theta \right) \quad (13)$$

$$(q_\theta)_2 = - \frac{K_{zh}}{\mu} \left(A_2 \cos \theta + \frac{A'_2}{r^2} \cos \theta \right) \quad (14)$$

At the interface $r=a$, we have

$$(V_r)_1 = (q_r)_2 \quad (15)$$

$$(\sigma_{r\theta})_1 = \mu \left[r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{V_\theta}{r} \right) + \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\partial V_r}{\partial \theta} \right) \right]_{r=a} = 0 \quad (16)$$

At the interface $r=b$, we have

$$(q_r)_2 = (q_r)_3 \quad (17)$$

$$p_2 = p_3 \quad (18)$$

The energy dissipation consistent condition is

$$V_\infty^2 \frac{\mu}{K_z} \pi b^2 = \int_0^a \int_0^{2\pi} e r d\theta dr + \int_a^b \int_0^{2\pi} (q_r^2 + q_\theta^2) \frac{\mu}{K_{zh}} r d\theta dr \quad (19)$$

with

$$e = 2\mu \left[\left(\frac{\partial V_r}{\partial r} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial V_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{V_r}{r} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial V_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial V_\theta}{\partial r} - \frac{V_\theta}{r} \right)^2 \right] \quad (20)$$

These relations complete the problem. The solution of K_z from this set of equations is

$$\frac{K_z}{K_{zh}} = \frac{1 + \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^2}{1 - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^2} \quad (21)$$

When the fiber packing within the insertion ($0 \leq r \leq b$) reaches the maximum, we assume this average fiber volume fraction within $0 \leq r \leq b$ is V_a since no flow is infiltrating into this insertion. At the same time, the fiber volume fraction in the ring section ($a \leq r \leq b$) reaches the maximum fiber volume fraction of the hexagonal packing, which is defined as V_{ah} . This V_{ah} is a definite value of $\pi(2\sqrt{3}) = 0.90690$. The value of V_a is related to the ratio of a to b and can be expressed as

$$\frac{a}{b} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{V_a}{V_{ah}}} \quad (22)$$

When the average fiber volume fraction of the insertion ($0 \leq r \leq b$) is V_f , the fiber volume fraction in the ring section ($a \leq r \leq b$) becomes

$$V_{fh} = \frac{V_f}{1 - a^2/b^2} \quad (23)$$

Since we assume in the ring section the packing is hexagonal, the permeability K_{zh} is a definite function of V_{fh} , or $K_{zh} = K_{zh}(V_{fh})$. The function form of $K_{zh}(V_{fh})$ has been studied by other workers. Sangani and Acrivos [8] proposed asymptotic solutions for drag coefficient of hexagonal and square packing structures. With the proposed approximation formula for hexagonal packing, the expression of K_z^* by using V_f and V_a becomes

$$K_z^* = 0.231 \left(\frac{1.814}{V_a} - 1 \right) \left[\frac{(1 - \sqrt{V_f/V_a})^{5/2}}{(V_f/V_a)} \right] \quad (24)$$

The constants in the expression are not curve fitting results but geometry factors.

We have also found that a slight change in the above expression gives out a better fitting for the hexagonal packing with numerical solutions within a range of V_f from 0.2 to 0.8. The suggested form then becomes

$$K_z^* = 0.229 \left(\frac{1.814}{V_a} - 1 \right) \left[\frac{(1 - \sqrt{V_f/V_a})}{(V_f/V_a)} \right]^{2.5} \quad (25)$$

Comparison of this model predictions for different packing structures and previous FE simulation results is shown in Fig. 3, where V_a values are chosen as 0.90690, 0.78540, 0.60460, and 0.58905 for hexagonal, square, hollow hexagonal, and hollow square packings respectively. Detailed finite element simulation results are presented in [9]. From the figure we can see that this improved SCM prediction follows other model at the low and middle range of V_f , and then follows Gutowski's model [2] trend in the high V_f range.

In both Kardos and Gutowski's studies, experimental measurements are conducted. In Kardos' experiment, the range of V_f is about 0.5 to 0.75. In Gutowski's experiment, these constants are derived by considering the consolidation of laminated composites, which

covers larger V_f ranges but the measurement of the permeability is indirect. In our numerical simulation, it is shown clearly that with a certain packing structure, when V_f is close to V_a of that packing, the transverse permeability decreases dramatically. This can be observed in Fig.3. More numerical data are presented in Fig. 4 with different hollow hexagonal and square packing patterns. Thus the values of V_a are different in these simulations. The so-called balance line method is used for the presentation, where the model predictions are plotted against values of numerical simulation.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

We have presented two self-consistent models for estimating the permeability of a fiber bundle in the transverse direction. In the improved self-consistent model, an additional parameter V_a other than fiber volume fraction V_f , is introduced to capture the imperfectness of a fiber bundle under practical conditions.

In the transverse flow case, the maximum packing V_a (also called available, attainable, or achievable fiber volume fraction) is proved to be a good indicator. This is due to the fact that the gaps between fibers is the main contributor to the transverse flow resistance. This parameter V_a to some extent correctly reflects the packing structure and also the gap status. More interesting is that it can be measured experimentally, as discussed in [2]. The formula derived from the model uses additional status variables for a fiber assembly, and gives good predictions for different fiber bundle conditions.

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Fig. 1: Illustration of the SCM and ISCM models

Fig. 2: Comparison of SCM predictions and other data

Fig. 3: Comparison of the predictions of improved SCM and other models

* Lines represent over and under 20% of the numerical solutions

Fig. 4: Comparison of FE simulation and self-consistent model predictions